

THE ROLE OF CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE SOCIAL LIFE OF OUR COUNTRY AND THE LEGAL BASIS OF THEIR DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article highlights the issue of improving the quality of personnel by the state in order to improve the corporate culture in cultural institutions in the conditions of the new Uzbekistan.

Key words: state, culture, cultural institutions, corporate culture, development.

Currently, the improvement of the development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in our country by the state is creating global changes. In recent years, large-scale works related to the introduction of new innovations are being carried out in the development of corporate culture in cultural institutions [1].

It is increasingly becoming a description of various objects, events and processes that are the result of the introduction of innovations in modern cultural institutions.

The fact that the state supports the development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan is characterized by the digitization and change of the industry, the emergence of cultural institutions and corporate culture. These processes are based on the creation of programs for the corresponding real processes of the development stage of corporate culture. In our view, corporate culture means a number of features of ideas, attitudes and behavior that allow people to unite into a single association (group) and enable them to achieve goals that are not possible for cultural institutions. Cultural institutions have their own tasks and goals that corporate culture fulfills.

At this point, let's focus on specific aspects of the relationship between the cultural institution and the corporate culture. The concept of "cultural institution" appeared in the scientific community relatively recently, corporate culture is its main content[2]. Corporate culture can emerge as a tool of strategic management of cultural institutions, create a motivational environment among team members, maintain and improve the system of public and personal values integrated for the implementation of the educational process.

In addition, state support for the development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan, the process of subject-object relations, on the one hand, is aimed at solving the problem of determining the quality of such relations in the environment of corporate culture, and achieving the goals and tasks of cultural institutions. In this regard, it is becoming an urgent task to solve the problem of determining the quality and effectiveness of such communications in the corporate cultural environment in cultural institutions, to find a solution to the problems of implementing the goals and tasks of cultural institutions.

They appear as carriers of corporate culture, dominant culture, and subculture. The dominant (dominant) culture is built on the basis of central, generally accepted values. In the process of state support for the development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan, it is important to consciously promote corporate culture in cultural institutions with concepts, content and cultural standards that have personal and professional significance [3].

It is related to the differentiation of narrow professional groups in cultural institutions and the creation of priorities in them. Thus, the dominant corporate culture is officially manifested

and accepted by the entire team, clearly expressed state support for the development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan is manifested among employees at the level of other manifestations of the direction. At this level, showing themselves as bearers of values, their relationship with students is carried out in professional and human relations.

The dominant culture of the development of corporate culture in cultural institutions in Uzbekistan has a formalized demonstrative nature and is included in the programs [4]. It is intended to be reflected in the behavior of future graduates in the way of their attitude to the main (central) values of their chosen profession and activity. Nevertheless, the implementation of educational programs with a corporate character, with educational aspects highlighted, cannot guarantee that the graduate will be fully introduced to the conditions of collective relations at the new workplace, because insufficient attention is paid to the formation of "corporate culture".

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